

Macquart, 1835, as a second junior synonym. Alternatively, some authors have claimed that *macrophthalma* was in fact a *Diasemopsis*, although all recent authors agreed on the synonym of *longicornis* and *thoracica*. In recent applied literature, both *macrophthalma* and *thoracica* have been used to indicate this stalk-eyed fly.

I have examined the *macrophthalma*, with the cooperation of the Stockholm Museum, and although the specimen was teneral and discolored it is unmistakably a *Diasemopsis*. The correct name of the African stem-boring stalk-eyed fly is *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart, 1835. Junior synonyms are *thoracica*

Westwood, 1837, and *phlogodes* Hendel, 1923. *Diopsis longicornis* is a common rice stem borer throughout Ethiopian Africa. Damage often is compensated for by the growing rice plants.

Other *Diopsidae* are mentioned as potentially important rice stem borers, among which is a stalk-eyed fly with apical wingpots. This fly has been identified as *Diopsis apicalis* Dalman, 1817, or *Diopsis tenuipes* Westwood, 1837. As part of a systematic revision of *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot, I have examined types of both species and find they are synonymous. However, about 10 *apicalis*-like *Diopsis* are found in rice in Africa. *Diopsis apicalis* (syn. *tenuipes*)

only occurs in West Africa, where it is the dominant *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot. In East, Central (up to Cameroon), and Southern Africa there is another, closely related, dominant *Diopsis* with an apical wingspot. This latter species and about eight other *Diopsis* with apical wingspots that occur in rice, maize, and other gramineous crops have yet to be described. Until I have published my revision of this group of *Diopsis*, it is best to refer to flies with apical wingpots as species belonging to the *apicalis*-complex. These flies are secondary stem borers, and lay eggs on shoots with deadhearts or other damage. *ℒ*

Seasonal stem borer (SB) population fluctuations in Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, several SB species attack rice and cause economic damage. We studied seasonal SB population fluctuations around the BINA farm from Jan to Dec 1982. Each week, 50 rice hills of the test fields were randomly sampled and SB larvae were removed from infested tillers. Populations of different species were recorded (see table).

From Jul-Oct, *Scirpophaga incertulas* constituted 60 to 97% of the SB population. From Nov to May, *Chilo*

Population of three SB species in Mymensingh, Bangladesh.

Mo	Percent of SB population		
	<i>S. incertulas</i>	<i>Chilo</i> sp.	<i>S. inferens</i>
Jan	25	56	19
Feb	4	85	11
Mar	2	71	21
Apr	21	19	60
May	20	61	19
Jun	—	—	—
Jul	79	21	0
Aug	60	38	2
Sep	97	0	3
Oct	76	24	0
Nov	9	62	29
Dec	21	56	17

polychrysa and *C. auricilia* constituted 19 to 85% of the population. The *Sesamia inferens* population always was low, but

increased from Nov to May, perhaps because wheat, an alternate host, is planted. *ℒ*

Changing populations of rice insect pests in Chhattisgarh, India

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Expanded irrigation, double-cropping,

and cultivation of N-responsive modern rices have changed insect populations in Chhattisgarh.

Populations of 12 common pests have not changed, but those of 10 are causing more damage (see table). *ℒ*

Status of rice pests in Chhattisgarh, India.^a

Insect	1960-70	1971-84
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i> (Guen.)	xx	xx
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i> (Stal.)	—	xx
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i> (Dist.)	xxx	xxx
<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i> (Motsch.)	xxx	xxx
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i> (Horva th)	xxx	xxx
<i>Orseolia oryzae</i> (W.M.)	x	xxx
<i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i> (Walker)	x	xxx
<i>Sesamia inferens</i> (Walker)	x	x
<i>Mythimna</i> spp.	xxx	xxx
<i>Nymphula depunctalis</i> (Guen.)	xx	xx
<i>Dichdispa armigera</i> (Oliv.)	xx	xx
<i>Pamara mathias</i> (F.)	x	x
<i>Hydrellia</i> sp.	x	x
<i>Baliothrips biformis</i> (Bagnall)	x	x
<i>Spodoptera</i> spp.	xx	xx
<i>Leptocorisa</i> spp.	x	x
<i>Irigonotylus doddi</i> (Dist.)	—	x
<i>Cymodema basicornis</i> (Motschulsky)	—	x
<i>Nanophyes</i> spp.	—	x
<i>Cryptocephalus ovulum</i> Suffrian	—	x
<i>C. sehestedtii</i> Fabricius	—	x
<i>Phyllotreta rhotonica</i> Quivivier	—	x

^a xxx = major pest causing severe damage, xx = minor pest causing occasionally heavy damage, x = minor pest; = not reported.